

MIRZO ULUG'BEK NOMIDAGI
O'ZBEKISTON MILLIY UNIVERSITETI
JIZZAX FILIALI

**KOMPYUTER ILMLARI VA
MUHANDISLIK TEXNOLOGIYALARI**

**XALQARO ILMIY-TEXNIK
ANJUMAN MATERIALLARI**

TO'PLAMI

1-QISM

26-27-SENTABR
2025-YIL

Google
Scholar

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI**

**MIRZO ULUG‘BEK NOMIDAGI O‘ZBEKISTON MILLIY
UNIVERSITETINING JIZZAX FILIALI**

**KOMPYUTER ILMLARI VA MUHANDISLIK
TEXNOLOGIYALARI**
*mavzusidagi Xalqaro ilmiy-texnik anjuman materiallari
to‘plami*
(2025-yil 26-27-sentabr)
1-QISM

JIZZAX-2025

CHEKLI ORALIQDA QISMAN SPEKRTAL SHTURM-LIUUVILL OPERATORI PARAMETLARINI TIKLASH

Abdunazarov Rabimkul

O'zbekiston Milliy universitetining Jizzax filiali

rabimkulabdunazaro@gmail.com

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada chekli oraliqda qisman izospektral Shturm-Liuivill operatori parametrini tiklash masalasi qaraladi.

Kalit so'zlar. Gelfand-Levitan integral tenglamasi, Shturm-Liuivill operatori, spectral berilganlar, teskari spectral masala, xos son, normallovchi o'zgarmas, xos funksiya, qisymiy-izospektral operator.

I.Kirish.

Berilgan $\lambda_0 < \lambda_1 < \lambda_2 < \dots \lambda_n < \dots$ sonlar ketma ketligi quyidagi

$$L(q(x), h, H)y \equiv -y'' + q(x)y = \lambda y, \quad (0 < x < \pi)$$

$$y'(0) - hy(0) = 0$$

$$y'(\pi) + Hy(\pi) = 0$$

chegaraviy masalaning xos qiymatlari, $\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots$ ketma ketliklar esa ushbu masalaning normallovchi sonlari bo'lsin. Ular uchun quyidagi yetarli katta $n > N$ dan boshlab quyidagi asimtotika o'rinli bo'lsin:

$$s_n = \sqrt{\lambda_n} = n + \frac{c_0}{\pi} + \frac{c_1}{n^3} + \dots$$

$$\alpha_n = \frac{\pi}{2} + \frac{b_0}{n^2} + \frac{b_1}{n^4} + \dots$$

Bu yerda c_0, c_1, b_0, b_1 lar berilgan haqiqiy sonlar.

Yuqoridagi shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi $\{\lambda_i, \alpha_i\}_{i=0}^{\infty}$ spectral berilganlarga ko'ra Shturm-Liuivill operatori parametrlarini tiklash masalasi I.M Gelfand va B. M. Levitan tomonidan tavsiya qilingan sxemasi bo'yicha amalga oshiriladi [1]. Bunda quyidagi munosabatlardan foydalaniladi

$$K(x, y) + F(x, y) + \int_0^x K(x, s)F(s, y)ds = 0$$

$$F(x, y) = \frac{\cos s_0 x \cos s_0 y}{\alpha_0} - \frac{1}{\pi} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{\cos s_k x \cos s_k y}{\alpha_k} - \frac{2 \cos kx \cos ky}{\pi} \right]$$

$$q(x) = 2 \frac{d}{dx} K(x, x), \quad h = K(0, 0) = -F(0, 0)$$

Ushbu maqolada chekli sondagi spectral berilgan bo'yisha Shturm-Liuivill operatori parametrlarini tiklash masalasi [2], [3], [4] tomonidan o'rganilgan algoritm bo'yicha aniq misollarda o'rganiladi. Natija va uning tahili quyidagi jadvalda kelririlgan.

Bunda H, h parametrlar ixtiyoriy tanlangan, $q(x)$ potensial funksiysifatida Bargmen potensialidan foydalanamiz.

$$q(x) = \frac{6\beta^2}{\cosh^2(\beta x - \gamma)}$$

Yuqorida anlangan potensial va boshqa parametrlar asosida λ_0, α_0 sonlarni topish, bu topilganlar asosida yuqorida keltirilgan algoritm bo'yicha $\tilde{h}, \tilde{H}, \tilde{q}(x)$ parametrlar quyidagi formulalar orqali hisoblanadi.

$$\tilde{q}(x) = 2dK(x, x) = 4s_0 \sin s_0 x \varphi(x, \lambda_0) + 2K^2(x, x)$$

$$K(x, x) = \left[\alpha_0 + \int_0^x \cos^2 s_0 t dt - (\pi - x) \cos^2 s_0 x - 2 \cos s_0 x \int_0^x \cos s_0 t dt \right]$$

$$/ \left(\alpha_0 (\pi - x) + \left(\int_0^x \cos s_0 t dt \right)^2 + (\pi - x) \int_0^x \cos^2 s_0 t dt \right)$$

$$\varphi(x, \lambda_0) = \alpha_0 \left((\pi - x) \cos s_0 x + \int_0^x \cos s_0 t dt \right)$$

$$/ \left(\alpha_0 (\pi - x) + \left(\int_0^x \cos s_0 t dt \right)^2 + (\pi - x) \int_0^x \cos^2 s_0 t dt \right)$$

$$\tilde{H} = s_0 \operatorname{ctg}(s_0 \pi) - s_0^2 \left(\alpha_0 + \frac{\pi}{2} \right) / \sin^2 s_0 \pi + \frac{s_0}{2} \operatorname{ctg} s_0 \pi, \quad \tilde{h} = \frac{1}{\pi} - \frac{1}{\alpha_0}$$

$\beta = 0.05,$ $\gamma = 50,$ $H=0.1,$ $h=-0.2$ $\lambda_0 = -0.057$ $\alpha_0 = 1.894245$	$\frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\pi q(x) - \tilde{q}(x) dx$	\tilde{H}	$\frac{ H - \tilde{H} }{H}$	\tilde{h}	$\frac{ h - \tilde{h} }{h}$	$\tilde{\alpha}_0$	$\frac{ \alpha_0 - \tilde{\alpha}_0 }{\alpha_0}$
	0.0831	0.105	0.05	0.207	0.035	1.888	0.004
$\beta = 0.1,$ $\gamma = 20,0$ $H = 1,0$ $h = 1.0$ $\lambda_0 = 0.4075$ $\alpha_0 = 7.08802$	0.112	0.115	0.066	0.863	0.092	6.171	0.407

Qaralayotgan $0 \leq x \leq \pi$ oraliq cheklarida $q(x)$ potensialning $q(0), q(\pi)$ qiymatlari formulalar yordamida aniqlanadi.

$$q(\pi) = 2 \sum_{k=1}^N (\lambda_n - n^2) + 2H^2 + 2 \left[s_n^2 \left(\frac{\varphi(\pi, \lambda_n)}{\cos s_n x} - 1 \right) + s_n \operatorname{tg}(s_n \pi) H \right]$$

$$q(0) = 2 \sum_{k=1}^N (\lambda_n - n^2) + 2h^2 - 2 \left[s_n^2 \left(\frac{\varphi(\pi, \lambda_n)}{\cos s_n x} - 1 \right) + s_n \operatorname{tg}(s_n \pi) H \right]$$

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Гельфанд И.М., Левитан Б.М «Об определении дифференциального уравнения по его спектральной функции». – Изв. АН СССР, сер.мат. -1951, т.15. -с.309-360.
2. R.Abdunazarov. Shturm- liuvill operatori parametrlarini tiklashda spektral berilganlarni almashtirish masalasi.Vol. 1 No. 2 (2025): Scientific and Innovative Research in Social Sciences and Humanities.
3. О. Э. Мирзаев, А. Б. Хасанов, О семействах изоспектральных краевых задач Штурма–Лиувилля, Уфим. матем. журн., 2020, том 12, выпуск 2, 28–34.
4. Абдуназаров, Р., & Жавбосов, И. (2024). Восстановление спектральные данные оператора Дирака по данным набором спектров. *Sambhram xabarnomasi*, 1(1), 256–259. Retrieved from <https://jurnal.sambhram.uz/index.php/JOURNAL/article/view/54>.

AYLANA AKSLANTIRISHLARIDA BURISH SONINING REZONANS KASRLARI VA ULARNING MAXRAJI HAQIDA TEOREMA

f.-m.f.f.d. Abduxakimov Saidaxmat Xazratkulovich,

Abduxakimova Maftuna G‘ofur qizi

O‘zbekiston Milliy universiteti Jizzax filiali

abduhakimova1995@gmail.com

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ishda burish soni ρ – irratsional bo‘lgan yo‘nalishni saqlovchi T aylana gomeomorfizmi qaralgan. T gomeomorfizmning burish sonlari $\rho^{(1)}(T) = \rho_f^{(1)} = [k_1, k_2, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_1, k_2, \dots]$, va $\rho^{(2)}(T) = \rho_f^{(2)} = [k_2, k_1, k_2, k_1, \dots, k_2, k_1, \dots]$, $k_1, k_2 \in N$ bo‘lganda $\frac{P_n}{q_n}$ munosib kasrning maxraji q_n uchun formulalar topilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Burish soni, yo‘nalishni saqlovchi aylana gomeomorfizmlari, munosib kasr.

Asosiy qism.

Dinamik sistemalar nazariyasida haqiqiy sonlarni uzluksiz kasrlarga yoyilmasi muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ixtiyoriy $\rho \in (0,1)$ haqiqiy sonni bir qiymatli quyidagi ko‘rinishda yoyiladi ([1]-[3]):